

HEALTH MONITORING SYSTEM FOR THE ELDERS AND INVALID

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a model health monitoring system for the elders and invalid. We propose a set of standard protocols for maintaining a centralised health monitoring station and design an outline for a multi-channel PC based wearable wireless device for monitoring health condition of the subject. It is intended to reduce the dependence of the target population on attendants, along with ensuring an efficient dispensation of quality health services, including emergency health care. As compared to the plethora of similar systems commercially available, this system has the advantage of being economically viable, while adhering to industry standards. Architectural details and schematic descriptions of the system are provided, along with an introductory review of the standards. It is modular and open-ended in architecture, enabling it to be customised as per requirements.

KEY WORDS

Medical informatics, Health care, Mobile computing, Networks, Telemedicine, P1073, MDDL, E1381, E1394, E1467, CBPR, CHIN, CDSS, Elders, Managed healthcare, Biotelemetry, Knowledgebase, Distributed computing

INTRODUCTION

Elder citizens and physically challenged people often find themselves in situations where they are dependent on others for mundane jobs relating to the monitoring of the state of their organisms. Their impaired motor, sensory and cognitive skills result in a difficulty to interact with their surroundings. This necessitates the presence of an attendant, restricting their free movement, and often leads to withdrawal and depressive symptoms. The situation can improve by the presence of a real-time continuous health-monitoring system, providing the target populace with much needed independence. There are many existing systems that conform to this role. However, their usage is restricted owing to lack of functionality, prohibitive costs, discomfiture in wearing, lack of supporting infrastructure and, above all, an unintuitive interface.

To answer these needs, we propose a PC based low-cost wearable health monitoring device, and a set of standard protocols for maintaining centralised health monitoring stations, for providing remote monitoring and quality health care services to the target population. It is scalable and adheres to industry standards in telemedicine for information storage, retrieval and transmission. Since the target population can only take partial care of themselves, the proposed system has an intuitive interface with speech and visual enhancements. It incorporates an inbuilt Clinical Decision Support System (CDSS) and lays the foundations for a large-scale managed Community Healthcare Information Network (CHIN). Above all, it is built from easily avail

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able components and offers a very low-cost solution.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Each subject wears a 3-piece wireless device, which communicates with a Home Unit (HU), a low end PC, using an audio FM link. The HU is connected to a Local Station (LS), implementing the P1073 Medical Interface Bus (MIB) interface over LAN or modem link. The LS connects to the Central Health Station (CHS) using ASTM E1381, E1394 and E1467 standards for transmission of medical data. The CHS collaborates with the Ambulance Unit, Experts' Panel, Administrative Units, and other hospital departments for providing quality health care to the subject. All medical records are stored and processed according to the HL7 Reference Information Model (RIM), providing smooth connectivity within, and with other health networks. Medical images are stored in electronic form using standards such as DICOM. Billing and pharmaceutical tasks employ NCPDP and X12N standards. As the Health Monitoring System (HMS) matures with new cases, an online medical knowledgebase is automatically generated. An inbuilt CDSS employs the knowledgebase to provide secondary support. Fig-1 gives a bird's-eye block diagram of the organisation of the system.

Figure1 : Organisational Structure

HEALTH MONITORING DEVICE

The health-monitoring device consists of three units: the chest pad, the arm strap and the waist pack. Fig-2 gives the schematic of the device as worn by a subject. The device collects photoplethysmograms for pulse oximetry, temperature, blood pressure, cardiac sounds and ECG for analysis by the HU. It connects to the HU using an audio FM link. This is accomplished by connecting an FM receiver to the computer audio-input, or by incorporating a dedicated FM tuner. The earlier option is preferred as the latter reduces cost benefit of the device. At the HU, special software analyses the signals received and implements a preset health policy for the subject. The HU interface is intuitively designed, with graphics prompts for the common operations, dialogues in the vernacular language of the subject and voice commands. However, most of the processes are automated and interaction is required only to provide the user added flexibility.

Figure2 : Schematic of the monitoring device as worn by a subject

ARM STRAP

The subject wears the arm strap on the left arm like a bracelet. An adjustable strap supports it. Its under-surface consists of grooves in which LEDs, photodiodes, temperature and pressure sensors are located. It also incorporates pre-amplifier and signal multiplexer circuits. Fig-3(a,b,c) gives a schematic of the arm strap.

The LEDs are turned on and off at a high frequency and the photodiode's output is amplified and sent to the multiplexer for Frequency Division Multiplexing (FDM). The outputs of the temperature and pressure sensors are also sent to the multiplexer at low frequencies. The multiplexed signal is carried to the chest piece along a thin pair of wires, where it is further multiplexed with other signals and sent to the waist pack for transmission.

The signal, on being received by the HU via the audio FM link, is demultiplexed to extract the photoplethysmograms and the other signals. The process of pulse oximetry is then implemented to monitor the subject's blood oxygen saturation and pulse. The photoplethysmography process can be extended to provide details of other constituents of blood and blood sugar levels. This remains as a further task.

Figure 3 : Arm Strap

CHEST PAD

The chest pad is supported on the left side of the subject's chest by a pair of adjustable straps. It consists of a stethoscope diaphragm, air coupled to a capacitive microphone, an ECG electrode, amplification circuit and a signal multiplexer. The chest pad's horizontal strap also supports another ECG electrode on the right side, completing the Einthoven triangle for ECG recordings. Fig-4 shows a block diagram of the chest pad's construction.

Figure 4 : Construction of the chest piece

The signals from the arm strap are further multiplexed along with the ECG and heart-sound signals at the chest pad. The multiplexed signal is finally carried down to

the waist-pack along another thin pair of wire cord.

The signal is received by the HU via the FM link. The chest sounds are analysed for detecting cardiac murmurs, splitting of heart sounds, thrills, respiratory rate and other clinically useful metrics.

WAIST PACK

The waist pack is a combo unit consisting of a low power FM transceiver, modulation circuits along with the third ECG electrode and the associated amplification circuit, and a 9V rechargeable battery pack. It is worn by the subject on the waist with the help of a clip. The ECG electrode is placed on this clip, such that it remains in contact with the subject's skin. The waist pack is represented in Fig-5(a,b,c). The composite signals from the arm strap, chest pad and ECG electrodes is modulated at FM frequencies and transmitted to the HU computer via its FM transceiver. The signals are keyed to prevent intermod from terrestrial FM channels.

Figure 5 : Waist pack

HOME UNIT

The Home Unit consists of a low-end computer, with a sound card. An FM transceiver is attached to the computer via the audio channel. The HU passes the composite signal it receives through cascaded demultiplexers to obtain the individual signals. The signal waveforms are then passed through predefined pattern analysers to test the state of the subject's organism. It is connected to the LS over LAN and implements the IEEE P1073 MIB interface. The communication syntax adheres to Medical Data Device Language (MDDL), which is an object oriented language defined by the P1073 standard. These make the wireless device, along with the HU, behave like a standard medical laboratory instrument and allow it to be used with other health networks as well.

Figure 6 : Home Unit

Under normal operating conditions the HU logs time averaged data locally, updating the LS database at intervals. However, when the HU finds the signals to be outside their threshold according to the health policy, it alerts the LS and the CHS.

The frequency of data being sent is increased and there can be provision for audio and video link-up with the LS or the CHS or any other department.

In an emergency situation these features can be extremely useful. As soon as the HU infers from the analysed signals that a clinical problem has occurred it sets on a two-fold task. First, it alerts the LS with a description of the nature of the problem detected, so that immediate help can arrive. Simultaneously it alerts the CHS, and the Ambulance Unit. The CHS support team can plan a course of action even before having arrived at the patient's residence. While in the traditional paramedic system, the ambulance team would only be able to gather physiological data once it reached the patient's place, this HMS provides them with the crucial data instantaneously and there is a systematic record of the onset of the problem. The ambulance team can further receive patient's data and be in touch with the team at the CHS by implementing mobile computing technologies such as wireless LAN. The system allows for proper resource utilisation as unnecessary deployment may be avoided, by analysing the patient's need from the CHS.

SUPPORT STATIONS

LOCAL STATION

The LS is community health centre nearest to the subjects' residence. This station is to be manned by skilled nurses and semi trained professionals. The connected HUs can give rise to alarms in case of an emergency, and hence the LS should ideally be within walking distance so that help can be rushed when needed. There should be local provisions at the LS for setting up IV infusion, oxygen and emergency records. The LS staff should be familiar with the subjects connected to it. The responsibilities of the LS include system maintenance, calibration of monitoring device, and general billing and administration. The LS connects to the CHS using the ASTM E1381 and E1394 standards for sharing data among lab computers, and the E1467 standard for exchange of physiological data. All the records transferred are stored according to the HL7 RIM schema, so that third party communication, for consulting the Experts Panel, in the middle of an emergency can be seamless. The LS is to have a direct audio-video-data link to the CHS, which can be utilised in an emergency.

CENTRAL HEALTH STATION

The CHS can be a department in a general hospital, or a dedicated hospital itself. Its manpower requirement is analogous to those of a regular hospital, with added telecommunication facilities. Staff under the CHS may be deployed to other departments, provided there exists a means for messaging them when needed. This can be accomplished by integrating Personal Digital Assistant (PDA) support into the CHS system. PDAs can be of further help to the HMS in general if they are wireless LAN enabled. For the effective functioning of the CHS as a department in a general hospital, other crucial departments should be connected to it implementing the HL7 RIM standard. The CHS is to utilise a CDSS, and the online medical knowledgebase. The CHS should collaborate with an Experts Panel, set up according

to government norms. The CHS should maintain standard classifications such as ICD-9-CM and CPT-4 for describing diseases to help achieve the model of globally networked medical support knowledgebase. The CHS can retrieve patients' medical images using the DICOM standard. The administrative and billing processes at the CHS are to be automated, implementing X12N and NCPDP standards to maintain privacy and check malpractice. The CHS should also implement a strong audit policy covering all the constituents of the CHS. As there are no acclaimed standards existing for auditing such a system, joint public and industry efforts should be made for its development.

DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS :

CLINICAL APPLICATION

Many of the emergency situations faced by the elderly or invalid population can be predicted or diagnosed by a combination of the parameters recorded by the monitoring device. This includes the four vital signs, viz. temperature, pulse, respiration and blood pressure, which are the staple tools of a physician. The following are the details of the recorded parameters.

- Temperature (in degrees Centigrade)
- Pulse (rate, rhythm, volume, type)
- Respiration (rate, rhythm, type)
- Blood pressure
- ECG (single lead)

Heart sounds (details of the apex beat, timing of cardiac cycle, valve closure, valve opening sounds and their splitting, murmurs, and friction rubs with their characteristics)

PULSE OXIMETRY

These parameters are analysed as explained earlier to predict and diagnose clinical conditions. For instance, a person predisposed to shock can be diagnosed by a combination of very low blood pressure, subnormal temperature, feeble and irregular pulse, and shallow and sighing respiration. The system also provides well-formatted parameter charts to the attending physician at the CHS.

STANDARDISATION REQUIREMENTS :

Standardisation is necessary to make the device open ended, that is, to allow it to communicate freely with other standard CHINs, be extendable and easily upgradeable. Standards in the fields of telemedicine, biotelemetry, clinical decision support and medical data interchange have been gradually forming over the past few decades and of late many systems have come to be accorded ISO status. Some of the standards used in the system are introduced here.

IEEE P1073 MEDICAL INTERFACE BUS :

The IEEE P1073 Medical Interface Bus provides a method for interconnecting medical instruments in a manner similar to the GPIB bus, used for connecting elec

tronics laboratory equipment. Devices based on varied architectures, implementing different methods of operation, can be coupled smoothly provided they incorporate the P1073 MIB.

The LS in the proposed system communicates with the HU over a LAN, implementing the P1073 MIB. The LS can reprogram the rate of transmission of various signals, via the HU, depending on the implemented policy. The device responds with the required signal, which may compose of raw or stochastic data. The plug-and-play capabilities of the MIB allow the monitoring device to be easily reconfigured as per the specific requirements of the patient. New patients can be attached to LS without much hassle as each patient's HU is given a unique identification number.

HL7 Reference Information Model :

HL7 Reference Information Model (RIM) allows consistent sharing and usage of data across various local contexts. It provides for data to be shared between different health networks, irrespective of the underlying schema used to build the database. The RIM can be expressed in Unified Modelling Language (UML), and hence used for object-based software development.

The incorporation of HL7 based 'views' in the proposed model database allows patient data to be easily exchanged between heterogeneous constituents of the HMS, and other health information networks and telemedicine groups. This also allows for easy maintenance and upgrade path for the database and coupling software. UML integration allows standard software engineering paradigms to be applied to improve reliability. It provides for the proposed HMS to be integrated with other managed health networks for the purpose of claims settlement and billing such as X12N. Moreover HL7 RIM uses ICD-9-CM code for classification of diseases.

ASTM E1381, E1394 and E1467 Standards :

The ASTM E1381, E1394 and E1467 standards define low and intermediate level protocols for exchange of clinical laboratory data and for connecting lab computers. These specifications address the low level protocol used for both serial binary data exchange and TCP/IP data exchange, and hence both the LAN and modem based communication requirements of the HMS are met by these protocols. By implementing these standards it is ensured that the system will work as per the levels specified by these standards and, when needed, include, or be included in, other CHINs.

CDSS and Medical Knowledgebase

Clinical Decision Support can be broadly defined as the use of information to help a clinician diagnose or treat a patient's health problem. The field of medicine changes constantly. Each day there are headlines about new ways to diagnose medical conditions, breakthroughs in treatments, and newly discovered ways to prevent health problems. It is not possible for any person to keep track of these developments mentally; this is where Clinical Decision Support becomes helpful by providing suggestions and hints. The HMS has an incorporated learning algorithm that

helps develop a knowledgebase automatically. A medical knowledgebase requires to be built per standards so that it can be integrated with other knowledgebases globally. The ASTM E1460 standard was discontinued in 1999, and there seems to be no acclaimed continuing standard in this field, with each application using its own standard. The HMS uses a raw data format for storing the knowledgebase, as this can easily be adapted to forthcoming standards. Hence, a standard for designing medical knowledgebase is a need of the hour.

COMPUTER BASED PATIENT RECORD

The Computer Based Patient Record (CBPR) has some subtle differences as compared to the Paper Based Patient Record (PBPR). These differences arise primarily owing to medico-legal and administrative problems. For instance, a patient may need a copy of his or her medical record for purposes such as insurance claim. However the concerned hospital may treat its electronic storage as confidential and deny access. On the administrative side, a PBPR need not be maintained as per standards, however CBPR has to adhere to standards. This owes primarily to the fact that most information in a CBPR is coded, and for effective interchange of information both the sending and the receiving parties need to follow the same standard. Besides, there is a variety of legislation bewildering which limits the development of efficient CBPR. Legislation and regulations need to be formulated for the efficient implementation of CBPR for the benefit of the society in general.

CLINICAL PROTOCOLS

Clinical Protocols (CP) are models of process of care for a given health problem. Although CPs, also known as Practice Guidelines, have been the topic of debates, their usage is almost necessary for the efficient utilisation of the HMS. A standard CP needs to be modified for use with HMS so as to incorporate all the events taking place in parallel. However, these need not be strictly enforced and should only serve as guidelines, allowing the clinician to apply her own wisdom and experience. The CPs for the HMS are integrated with the CDSS.

ERGONOMICS, DESIGN AND FABRICATION :

The arm unit is fabricated as a bracelet and the chest strap, along with a waist mountable battery pack. The straps need to be fabricated from material suitable for extended wearing. The devices should avoid materials to which some people can be allergic. The chest pad and arm strap use rigid mountings in the present device. Further work is needed to provide for the usage of flexible mountings for increased comfort. The waist pack can be made lighter by using lower power batteries. This requires further work towards reducing power consumption.

LOCALISED AND NATURAL INTERFACE :

Dialogs are localised in the language of the target population. This can be a chore if the dialogs are to be individually ported to each language. A single meta-language description of dialogs can be designed. Machine translation can then be used to convert the dialog resource to the required vernacular.

Natural Language Interface provides a step further into user oriented design. Recent strides in this field have made Continuous Speech Recognition possible for low-end desktops. The HMS incorporates speech commands for hands free operation and for easy access, however it is restricted to a limited vocabulary of redundant discrete speech commands.

MOBILITY CONSIDERATIONS

The monitoring device, despite its usefulness, restricts the subject's mobility to within range of the audio FM link. Incorporating processing into the device itself and connecting it to the LS using wireless LAN could better the situation. However wireless LAN is an expensive alternative and goes against the primary principle of making the system affordable. Providing wireless LAN capabilities and on device processing can certainly be an area of further research.

DATABASES

The data generated by the monitoring device is to the tune of a few MBs per second. This figure can run into an enormous amount and combined with the storage requirements for the other electronic records for the patient, which include medical images, it can be in the range of a few hundred GB per patient per month. It surely would be uneconomical to store such vast amount of data at any centralised facility in the raw form. The solution certainly lies in data compression. However, even with compressed data searching can become inefficient. Therefore, to improve performance, the HMS uses a distributed database system, utilising the resources available at the LS.

INFERENCE AND DATA-MINING ENGINES :

Clinical Decision Support requires an inference engine to utilise the knowledgebase. The inference engine utilises fuzzy neural nets to identify patterns in the cases encountered and updates the database accordingly. In the support phase, whenever the error difference between the pattern of a clinical case and an entry in the knowledgebase falls below a threshold, the entry is presumed to be of interest to the clinician and is shown as reference. However this is only a limited application solution and further robust methods can be designed.

DISTRIBUTED AND PARALLEL COMPUTING :

The processing needs for the system are enormous at the LS and the CHS. One solution is to employ a high-end super-computing solution, but this is plausible only if there is a very large subscriber base to the HMS, offsetting the cost. An innovative solution is to utilise distributed parallel processing. The HMS implements a Parallel Virtual Machine (PVM) using the low-end workstations connected to it. A discussion of this implementation is a topic in its own right. However, only a subset of the total problem domain has been parallelised as yet and some programs can be tricky to parallelise.

Available API's:

The economy of the system is further improved by the use of standard Application Programming Interfaces (API) available for problem sub-sets. Many companies have come out with speech recognition and telephony API. The numerical elements in the HMS borrow heavily from lapack, linpack and scalapack, which are libraries of numerical methods.

SECURITY & STABILITY :

The growth in computer related crimes and frauds have led to the identification of the problem of security in any computing systems. Even more for an open system like the HMS. The immediate threats are from disgruntled attackers and virulent code. Implementing the strictest security policy, including those for the physical location of the hardware, only can solve this problem. These topic needs to be deeply probed before full-scale implementation of the HMS and the system should go through all the phases of medical system development, including clinical pilot-study, before general deployment, owing to its life-supporting nature.

However, even in a limited and controlled environment pilot studies can face stability problems from unreliable computer systems. A formal analysis is, therefore, warranted for all the software components. The critical hardware should be within medically acceptable tolerance limits.

COST EFFICIENCY/BENEFITS

The cost efficiency of the system is obvious when the actual cost of the device is compared to other alternatives. An average system inclusive of a low end PC, arm strap, chest pad, waist pack and an FM transceiver costs up to 10 times less. The costs benefits of this system need to be analysed as tangible and intangible costs, with the each being equally relevant. The target population saves added expenditure in terms of unnecessary tests, and can be better employed besides becoming self-reliant, further increasing benefits. A full featured Cost Efficiency Analysis (CEA) and Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA) can be helpful in highlighting these cost gains from this system.

CONCLUSION AND FURTHER WORK

In this paper we have presented a model health monitoring system for the elderly and invalid along with a set of standard protocols for maintaining a centralised health monitoring station and have designed an outline for a multi-channel PC based wearable wireless device for monitoring health condition of the subject. A discussion of the kind of medical problems the device can alleviate is followed by an introductory review of the standards implemented, along with other design considerations. It is modular and open-ended in architecture, enabling it to be customised as per requirements, has an intuitive natural interface and is cost effective. There are many venues of further development, which include designing a standard for medical knowledgebase, ergonomics of the wearable device, instrumentation for monitoring blood-sugar levels, parallelising algorithms, enhancing security, analysing legislative and regulatory requirements and, above all, field studies.

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